

Mental Health of Male and Female Professional Course Students: A Comparative Study

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Abstract: Mental health is a main factor for individuals, families and communities, and is more than simply the absence of a mental disorder. In this paper, there is a comparison between the mental health of male and female professional course students. We use null hypothesis method for observing the mental health of male and female professional course students of HNB Garhwal University, Srinagar, and Uttarakhand. We take a null hypothesis that there is no significant difference in Mental Health according to the gender of professional course students. This research is conducted on the basis of questionnaire tool “Mental Health Questionnaire as Mental Health Battery” by Arun Kumar Singh and Alpana Sen Gupta. After analyzing the collected data, our findings are there is an effect of the gender of students in emotional stability; Overall Adjustment and Security-Insecurity but we did not find any significance difference in Autonomy, Self-Concept, Intelligence and Overall Mental Health. These are the factors Mental Health.

I. INTRODUCTION

Mental health is defined by the World Health Organization (WHO) as “a state of well-being in which the individual realizes his or her own abilities, can cope with the normal stresses of life, can work productively and fruitfully, and is able to make a contribution to his or her community”. Good mental health is not just the absence of mental health problems. Individuals have some virtue with good mental health:

- develop emotionally, creatively, intellectually and spiritually
- initiate, develop and sustain mutually satisfying personal relationships
- face problems, resolve them and learn from them
- are confident and assertive
- are aware of others and empathize with them
- use and enjoy loneliness
- play and have fun

The objective of this study is to compare the mental health of the students according to their gender i.e. male and female. The study was conducted on 120 professional course students of the following three colleges of HNB Garhwal central university at Chauras campus:

1. School of Engineering and Technology.
2. School of Pharmacy.
3. School of Management.

The study has been limited to the students of only three professional courses i.e. B.Tech, B.Pharm and MBA and the study is directed toward the students with in age range from 18 to 24 years.

II. METHOD

This research is conducted on the basis of questionnaire survey on the students of professional courses of different colleges of the HNB Garhwal central university in chauras. We take three professional courses like B.Tech., B.Pharm., MBA for this study and categories these courses in to two part first one is under graduate and second one is post graduate level. In this study, we take samples on the basis of simple random sampling. It means that every member of the sample is selected from these three courses in such a manner that all members of these courses have essentially the probability of being selected.

Procedure

The students had to attempt total 130 questions according to the instructions given in the tool, “Mental Health Questionnaire as Mental Health Battery” by Arun Kumar Singh and Alpana Sen Gupta, which is used in this study.

In this tool, the questions are distributed according to the six different areas which are the key features of mental health. These areas are:

Table: 1

Part	Area	Total No. of Questions
I	Emotional Stability	15
II	Overall Adjustment	40
III	Autonomy	15
IV	Security and Insecurity	15
V	Self-Concept	15
VI	Intelligence	30
Total		130

- 1. Emotional Stability:** It refers to experiencing subjective stable feeling which has positive or negative values for the individual.
- 2. Overall Adjustment:** It refers to the individual's achieving an overall harmonious balance between the demands of various aspects of environment, such as home, health, social, emotional and school on the one hand and cognition on the other.
- 3. Autonomy:** It refers to a stage of independence and self-determination in thinking.
- 4. Security and Insecurity:** It refers to a high (or low) sense of safety, confidence, and freedom from fear, apprehension or anxiety particularly with respect to fulfilling the person's present or future needs.
- 5. Self-Concept:** It refers to the sum total of the person's attitudes and knowledge towards himself and evaluation of his achievements.
- 6. Intelligence:** It refers to general mental ability which helps the person in thinking rationally, and in behaving purposefully in his environment.

Hypothesis for this study are taken as:

1. No significant difference in emotional stability according to the gender of professional course students.
2. No significant difference in Overall Adjustment according to the gender of professional course students.
3. No significant difference in Autonomy according to the gender of professional course students.
4. No significant difference in Security and Insecurity according to the gender of professional course students.
5. No significant difference in Self-Concept according to the gender of professional course students.
6. No significant difference in Intelligence according to the gender of professional course students.

III. STATISTICAL DATA CALCULATION

The data are collected according to the MHB and these scores are about the response pattern of the subject on each test of investigation. After collecting all score for all the students, researcher tabulates this data and fined its Statistical Data response by using the Statistical techniques. Firstly the score of the subjects for every respective area were tabulated through the formulae of mean, deviation and critical ratio. These calculations were calculated by using following formulas.

Mean(M)

For a data set, the mean is the sum of the observations divided by the number of observations. It identifies the central location of the data, sometimes referred to in English as the average. The mean is calculated using the following formula.

$$M = \frac{\sum(X)}{N}$$

Where Σ = Sum of

X = Individual data points

N = Sample size (number of data points)

Standard Deviation(S)

The standard deviation is the most common measure of variability, measuring the spread of the data set and the relationship of the mean to the rest of the data. Conversely, if many data points are far from the mean, indicating that there is a wide variance in the responses, then the standard deviation will be large. If all the data values are equal, then the standard deviation will be zero. The standard deviation is calculated using the following formula.

$$S = \sqrt{\frac{\sum(X-M)^2}{N}}$$

Where Σ = Sum of

X = Individual score

M = Mean of all scores

N = Sample size (number of scores)

Standard Error Difference(SE_d)

It is the standard error of the difference between two means. The Standard Error Difference is calculated using the following formula.

$$SE_d = \sqrt{[(S_1^2/N_1) + S_2^2/N_2]}$$

Where S_1^2 = Square of the deviation of first sampling

S_2^2 = Square of the deviation of second sampling

N_1 = Number of first sample

N_2 = Number of second sample

Critical Ratio(CR)

It is used to calculate the statistical significance of their difference between an experimental and a control means, if the experimental sample group and the control sample group and randomly selected from the population.

$$CR = |M_1 - M_2| / SE_d$$

Where $|M_1 - M_2|$ = Mean Difference between both sampling group

SE_d = Standard Error Difference

IV. ANALYSIS AND RESULT

The data is collected from the students according to their six different features. This analyzed data is tabulated below according to the gender the students and a standard deviation is calculated in each category of analysis.

1. ES- Emotional Stability

Table2

Group The gender	No. of Students	Mean	SD	CR	Level Significance of
Male	71	10.8169	2.043953	3.425675	Significance Difference at .05 level
Female	49	9.612245	1.782183		

Result: The study of Emotional Stability (ES) of the professional courses students on the basis of their gender (Male or Female) is shown above in tabular form (Table No. 2). After analyzing the whole data, the CR (Critical Ratio) is found to be 3.426 which is significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the hypothesis 1(v) is rejected.

2. OA-Overall Adjustment

Table3

Group The gender	No. of Students	Mean	SD	CR	Level Significance of
Male	71	28.22535	3.670197	2.804512	Significance Difference at .05 level
Female	49	26.42857	3.288818		

Result: The study of Overall Adjustment (OA) of the professional courses students on the basis of their gender (Male or Female) is shown above in tabular form (Table No. 3). After analyzing the whole data, the CR (Critical Ratio) is found to be 2.805 which is significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the hypothesis 2(v) is rejected.

3. AY-Autonomy

Table4

Group The gender	No. of Students	Mean	SD	CR	Level Significance of
Male	71	10.30986	1.632345	0.200444	No Significance Difference at .05 level
Female	49	10.36735	1.480401		

Result: The study of Autonomy (AY) of the professional courses students on the basis of their gender (Male or Female) is shown above in tabular form (Table No. 4). After analysing the whole data, the CR (Critical Ratio) is found to be 0.200 which is non-significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the hypothesis 3(v) is accepted.

4. SI-Security-Insecurity

Table5

Group The gender	No. of Students	Mean	SD	CR	Level Significance of
Male	71	8.647887	1.628086	3.663828	Significance Difference at .05 level
Female	49	9.959184	2.108865		

Result: The study of Security-Insecurity (SI) of the professional courses students on the basis of their gender (Male or Female) is shown above in tabular form (Table No. 5). After analyzing the whole data, the CR (Critical Ratio) is found to be 3.664 which is significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the hypothesis 4(v) is rejected.

5. SC-Self-Concept

Table6

Group the Gender	No. of Students	Mean	SD	CR	Level of Significance
Male	71	7.915493	1.882061	0.498891	No Significance Difference at .05 level
Female	49	7.734694	1.997708		

Result: The study of Self-Concept (SC) of the professional courses students on the basis of their gender (Male or Female) is shown above in tabular form (Table No. 6). After analyzing the whole data, the CR (Critical Ratio) is found to be 0.499 which is non-significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the hypothesis 5(v) is accepted.

6. IN-Intelligence

Table7

Group The gender	No. of Students	Mean	SD	CR	Level of Significance
Male	71	22.16901	2.175316	0.866494	No Significance Difference at .05 level
Female	49	22.5102	2.081232		

Result: The study of Intelligence (IN) of the professional courses students on the basis of their gender (Male or Female) is shown above in tabular form (Table No. 7). After analyzing the whole data, the CR (Critical Ratio) is found to be 0.866 which is non-significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the hypothesis 6(v) is accepted.

7. Overall Mental Health

Table8

Group The gender	No. of Students	Mean	SD	CR	Level of Significance
Male	71	88.08451	7.655885	1.157595	No Significance Difference at .05 level
Female	49	86.61224	6.229673		

Result: The study of Overall Mental Health of the professional courses students on the basis of their gender (Male or Female) is shown above in tabular form (Table No. 8). After analyzing the whole data, the CR (Critical Ratio) is found to be 1.158 which is non-significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the hypothesis 7(v) is accepted.

V. CONCLUSION

On the basis of the standard deviation derived from statistical analysis, the following findings are found:

1. There is an effect of the gender (Male or Female) of the professional course students on the Emotional Stability (ES).
2. There is an effect of the gender (Male or Female) of the professional course students on the Overall Adjustment (OA).
3. There is no effect of the gender (Male or Female) of the professional course students on the Autonomy (AY).
4. There is an effect of the gender (Male or Female) of the professional course students on the Security-Insecurity (SI).
5. There is no effect of the gender (Male or Female) of the professional course students on the Self-Concept (SC).
6. There is no effect of the gender (Male or Female) of the professional course students on the Intelligence (IN).

After analysing above findings we conclude our study with the result that there is no effect of the gender (Male or Female) of the student on the Overall Mental Health of professional course students.

Suggestions for Future

Although the result is obtain under small number of students of professional courses but study can get more precise result by increasing the weight of sample i.e. the number of students. In future, the symmetric and systematic research can also be done for improving the quality of professional courses as well as professional course students in our country. According to my study, there are some suggestions for future work which would be done for development of professional education.

1. A comparative study may be done on more professional courses students other than B.Tech, B.Pharm and MBA.
2. A comparative study can also be conducted in some other professional institutes and universities of India.
3. A large sample may be used by covering whole state as well as whole country.
4. A study may be conducted on the various other factors of mental health and its effect on academic achievements.

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